

Organo-antimony Compounds.

Part I.

BY SUDHIR CHANDRA NIYOGY.

The object of this investigation was to find the relation, if any, that exists between the physiological action and chemical composition of the halogen substitution products of sodium *p*-acetylaminophenyl stibinate.

The first compound of this type, sodium 4-acetyl-amino-3-chlorophenyl stibinate (known in the trade as Von Heyden's 471) had already been described by Brahmachari and Das (*Ind. J. Med. Research*, 13, 17). Previously this compound was largely used for the treatment of kala-azar but has now been superseded by ureastibamine (Brahmachari, *Ind. J. Med. Research*, 1922, 10, 492), the carbamino derivative of the ammonium salt of *p*-aminophenyl stibinic acid. A study of the action of these two antimony compounds brings out a remarkable fact. According to opinion of medical profession, Von Heyden's 471 and ureastibamine are equally active at first after but a time the action of Von Heyden's preparation begins perceptibly to fall off, while that of ureastibamine continues the same as before (private communication). The conclusion that can be drawn from this difference in the activity appears to be that after a patient has been given a certain number of injections of Von Heyden's preparation, the system becomes tolerant to it and so no further improvement takes place. This led the author to prepare other halogen substituted derivatives in the hope that the inefficiency of Von Heyden's compound may be removed and the medical profession may be provided with a suitable and stable substance (ureastibamine is very unstable) for combating kala-azar.

Brahmachari (*loc. cit.*) described the preparation and properties of some derivatives of *p*-aminophenyl stibinic acid; Macallum (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 468T) described *o*-aminophenyl stibinic acid; whilst recently Dunning and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2959) described some azo-derivatives of *p*-aminophenyl stibinic acid; and Schmidt (*Annalen*, 1922, 429, 145) the preparation of *p*-amino-*p*-hydroxy- and *m*-nitro-phenyl stibinic acid and their salts.

The starting point was in each case *p*-nitraniline and the mono- and di-*ortho*-substituted halogen derivatives were prepared by the

usual methods (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1564; 1882, 15, 474; 1877, 10, 1709; 1875, 8, 148; 1878, 11, 144; 1901, 34, 8844; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1778; D. R. P. 109189).

The acetylation of these compounds was carried out by Orton's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1242). It was found however that mono-*ortho*-substituted amines could not be completely acetylated in the absence of sulphuric acid—an observation which disproves Orton's statement that mineral acids depress rather than accelerate the rate of acetylation of mono-*ortho*-substituted amines.

The reduction of these nitro-compounds to obtain the corresponding amines gave rise to considerable difficulty. The usual reducing agents were not quite satisfactory. The operation was successfully carried out by leading sulphuretted hydrogen into an alcoholic solution of the nitro body saturated with dry ammonia.

The preparation of the corresponding antimony compounds from these amines was found to be an extremely difficult and tedious operation. As had been stated in a previous paper (*this Journal*, 1927, 4, 96), it was always found more satisfactory to carry out the operation by the gradual addition of caustic soda solution to a suspension in water of the additive compound of the diazo-salt with antimony trichloride. But even with this method the difficulties were numerous. In some cases the decomposition of the diazo-compound was so rapid that the product isolated was the corresponding phenol. In others again, the nitrogen evolved during the reaction formed a stiff foam which prevented thorough mixing and the yield was poor. It is essential for the success of the operation that the stirring must be very vigorous, so that the contents are always thoroughly mixed up and the decomposition of the diazo-compound is not localised.

The physiological action of these antimony compounds is now being investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Bromo-4-nitraniline.—*p*-Nitranniline (10 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (150 c.c.) with warming. The solution was then cooled to room temperature. Bromine (12 g.) in acetic acid was slowly added to the solution of nitraniline with stirring. The absorption of bromine was very rapid. Towards the end, a yellowish white precipitate separated and hydrobromic acid was evolved. The reaction mixture was then heated on a water-bath for about 30

minutes and then filtered off and washed thoroughly with water; m. p. 100-2°. Yield—14 gm. (The m. p. of 2-bromo-4-nitraniline, prepared by brominating *p*-nitroacetanilide and subsequent hydrolysis, as given in the literature is 104-105°).

2:6-Dibromo-4-nitraniline.—In this preparation the weight of bromine used was twice as much as in the former case and the solution of bromine was added to a hot solution of *p*-nitraniline in acetic acid. Yield (from 10 gm. *p*-nitraniline) 19 gm.; m. p. 204-5°.

2-Iodo-4-nitraniline and *2:6-Di-iodo-4-nitraniline* were prepared by the method of Willgerodt and Arnold (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3844). The yield was quite satisfactory.

2:6-Dichloro-4-nitraniline.—This compound was at first prepared according to Flürscheim's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1773). But as this method required a large expenditure of acetic acid and hydrochloric acid, it was found more economical to prepare it according to the specification of Cassella & Co's patent (D. R. P. 109189), which is given out to be a process for preparing 2-chloro-4-nitraniline but was found to give 2:6-dichloro-4-nitraniline under all conditions.

Acetylation.—Orton's method (*loc. cit.*) was in each case employed, and the yields were quite satisfactory, the products being pure except in the case of 2:6-di-iodo-4-nitraniline which had to be recrystallised.

4-Acetylamino-3:5-di-iodo-1-nitrobenzene.—2:6-Di-iodo-4-nitraniline (12 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (120 c.c.) and to this was added acetic anhydride (60 c.c.). About 20-24 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were then added to this suspension when the whole went into solution and the colour changed from yellow to light brown. This was allowed to stand for about an hour and poured into a litre of boiling water. On cooling, a light brown precipitate, m. p. 235-38°. separated. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol the m. p. rose to 245-46°. Yield 10 gm. (Found: N, 7.04. $C_8H_6O_3N_2I_2$ requires N, 6.46 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3-iodo-1-nitrobenzene.—Yellowish white glistening plates, m. p. 183-39°. Yield 9.5 gm. from 10 gm. of 2-iodo-4-nitraniline. (Found: N, 9.58. $C_8H_6O_3N_2I$ requires N, 9.14 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-dichloro-anilins.—4-Acetylamino-3:4-dichloro-1-nitrobenzene (5 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol with gentle warming (the volume of alcohol added must be such that the nitro compound does not separate on cooling). The alcoholic solution was then saturated with dry ammonia and treated with a slow current of hydrogen sulphide for 3 hours. The solution was then evaporated

to dryness on a water-bath and the residue extracted with water and filtered. The clear filtrate, on cooling, gave light flaky crystals, which after two recrystallisations from water melted at 209—10°. Yield 2 gm. (Found: N, 12·97. $C_8H_8ON_2Cl$ requires N, 12·78 per cent.).

Reduction of 4-Acetylamino-3-bromo-1-nitrobenzene.—A rather remarkable compound was isolated in the course of this reducing operation. After an alcoholic ammonia solution of 4-acetylamino-3-bromo-1-nitrobenzene had been saturated with hydrogen sulphide, the whole was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue consisted of the amino body mixed with sulphur. In some cases, it was found extremely difficult to separate this impurity. It was found that sulphur was soluble in warm pyridine and the whole of it separated upon somewhat diluting the solution. The mixture of the amine and sulphur was dissolved in pyridine and diluted with a few drops of water. A yellow precipitate separated which was filtered off and found to be sulphur. On further diluting the filtrate a yellow crystalline precipitate separated, which after recrystallisation from pyridine melted at 270-72° whereas the m.p. of 4-acetylamino-3-bromo-aniline is 120-21°. The yellow product was found to be insoluble in common organic solvents, except pyridine and to give no diazo reaction. On analysis it was found to contain 6·5% nitrogen, the required amine containing 12·22%. The constitution of this is being investigated and will be communicated in due time.

4-Acetylamino-3-bromo-aniline.—4-Acetylamino-3-bromo-1-nitrobenzene (7 g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit, cooled and liquor ammonia added and then saturated with H_2S . The residue obtained by evaporating the ammoniacal solution, after being extracted with water (twice) and on cooling in ice, did not give any precipitate. The whole was then evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator when a yellow oily residue was left, easily soluble in water, alcohol and chloroform and giving the usual diazo reaction. After being left in a vacuum desiccator for a few days and on occasionally scratching with a glass rod, the oil was converted into a semi-solid mass which was then extracted with benzene. On cooling the benzene solution in ice water, white plates, m.p. 110-12°, separated. Recrystallised from benzene these had m.p. 120-21°. Yield 3 gm. (Found: N, 11·56. $C_8H_8ON_2Br$ requires N, 12·22 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-dibromo-aniline—similar to 4-acetylamino-3:5-dichloroaniline. M.p. 285-86°. Yield (from 9 gm. nitro compound)

3.5 gm. (Found: N, 9.05. $C_8H_8ON_2Br$, requires N, 9.09 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3-iodo-aniline.—4-Acetylamino-3-iodo-1-nitrobenzene (7 gm.) was dissolved in alcohol, saturated first with ammonia and then with sulphuretted hydrogen for 4 hours. On evaporation a yellow pasty mass was left. This was twice extracted with carbon disulphide and then with petroleum ether to remove sulphur. The residue was thrice extracted with benzene and the yellow benzene extract was decolourised by animal charcoal and filtered. On cooling in ice, a white crystalline precipitate separated, melting at 132-84°, and on crystallisation from benzene the melting point rose to 134-85°. Yield, 2.7 gm. (Found: N, 9.72. $C_8H_8ON_2I$ requires N, 10.14 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-di-iodo-aniline.—The corresponding nitro compound was treated as described in the previous cases. But all attempts to purify the amine from sulphur by the method described above failed. This was, however, effected as follows: The residue obtained by evaporating the alcoholic solution was again dissolved in absolute alcohol and copper powder (prepared by precipitating copper sulphate with zinc dust) was added to it and boiled under reflux, till the red colour of metallic copper had almost disappeared. The liquid was then filtered off from the precipitated copper sulphide and evaporated on a water-bath. Twice during this operation a gelatinous precipitate of copper sulphide was formed which was removed and the whole evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue, now found to be free from sulphur, was boiled with methyl alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on dilution gave a precipitate melting at 240-48°. On recrystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol the melting point rose to 247-48°. Yield (from 8 gm. nitro derivative) 8 gm. (Found: N, 7.03. $C_{10}H_8ON_2I_2$, requires N, 6.96 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-dichlorophenyl Stibinate of Sodium.—4-Acetylamino-3:5-dichloro-aniline (2.5 g.) was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). This was cooled to 0° and diazotised. Hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) was further added. To this diazo solution was then added antimony trichloride solution prepared by dissolving antimony trioxide (2 g.) in hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.). A yellowish white precipitate immediately separated which was left to stand in ice for half an hour with occasional stirring. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid

and then with water till acid free. The moist mass was then beaten up with water cooled to 5—7° and sodium hydroxide (6 g.) dissolved in water was gradually added with vigorous stirring. The stirring was continued till the evolution of nitrogen slackened. The liquid was then filtered off and the clear filtrate acidified with dilute acetic acid when the free antimonious acid separated as a flocculent precipitate; it was washed with water till free from acid. The free acid was then suspended in water, dissolved by adding a dilute solution of sodium carbonate drop by drop and filtered off from the insoluble impurities, if any. The solution was then concentrated on a water-bath; a small quantity was removed and absolute alcohol added in large excess. But as no precipitate separated, the concentrated solution was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator and the dark coloured residue extracted with methyl alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. On adding ether, the sodium salt of the antimonious acid separated as a faintly pink gelatinous precipitate, which was filtered off, washed with ether and finally dried in a vacuum over paraffin. (Found: N, 3·7; Sb, 29·9. $C_2H_7O_4NCl_2SbNa$ requires N, 3·5; Sb, 30·4 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3-stibinate of sodium was prepared as above. (Found: C, 23·64; Sb, 29·01. $C_8H_9O_4NBrSbNa$ requires C, 23·7; Sb, 29·6 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-dibromophenyl stibinate of Sodium. (Found: C, 20·13; Sb, 25·2. $C_8H_7O_4NBr_2SbNa$ requires C, 19·8; Sb, 24·8 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3-iodophenyl stibinate of Sodium. (Found: C, 21·5; Sb, 25·9. $C_8H_7O_4NISbNa$ requires C, 21·2; Sb, 26·6 per cent.).

4-Acetylamino-3:5-di-iodophenyl stibinate of Sodium. (Found: C, 17·48; Sb, 21·4. $C_8H_5O_4NI_2SbNa$ requires C, 16·8; Sb, 20·5 per cent.).

Properties.—The dried sodium salts are faintly red amorphous powders, fairly soluble in water forming a red solution with a neutral reaction (litmus). On acidifying with dilute mineral acid the free acid is precipitated which can again be dissolved in dilute alkali. Some of these compounds were found to be extremely hygroscopic.

I desire to convey my thanks to Prof. H. K. Sen for the interest he has taken in the course of this work and also to Mr. K. C. Bose-Ray for having helped me in the analytical portion of the work.